

Recommended Procedure

5 ml of ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer (pH adjusted to 10), 1 ml of sodium perchlorate (1 M), 1 ml of the oxime solution ($10^{-1}M$), 0.5 ml pyridine and different aliquots of $MnSO_4$ solution ($10^{-3}M$) are taken in a 25 ml separatory funnel. The volume of the aqueous phase is maintained at 10 ml by adding requisite volume of distilled water, 10 ml of toluene is added to the contents of the funnel and shaken well, for five minutes. After equilibration, the organic layer is separated, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the absorbance measured against solvent blank at 420 nm. The organic phase obtained in the extraction carried out without the metal ion is used as the solvent blank. The good linear plot obtained between the amount of the metal ion and the absorbance showed that manganese can be estimated by the present method accurately in the range 0-6 $\mu g/ml$. The molar absorptivity (ϵ) and the Sandell sensitivity (S) at 420 nm are 0.58×10^4 lit. mole $^{-1}$ cm $^{-1}$ and 0.0095 $\mu g/cm^2$ respectively. The standard deviation is 0.005. Zn(II) and Ni(II) do not interfere. More than 2 fold excess of Fe(III) interferes in the determination.

The Coleman⁶ graphical analysis of the organic layer showed that only a single species is responsible for the colour of the organic phase. Absorbance of the toluene layer increased with increase of pyridine upto 5% and later remains constant.

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Thermal Studies of Absorption Behaviour of Some Organic Compounds on Partially Co(II) and Ni(II)-Exchanged AW500 Zeolites

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PARTIALLY cation-exchanged samples of synthetic zeolite AW500 were prepared with cobalt(II) chloride-hexahydrate and nickel(II) chloride-hexahydrate. Thermal behaviours of these zeolites after interaction with pyridine, triethanol amine, trichloroethylene and 1, 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane have been investigated by thermogravimetry, differential thermal analysis and differential thermogravimetry. Experimental details and the thermal behaviours of these exchanged samples along with data on absorbed samples of partially-exchanged Cu(II) and Hg(II)-AW500 with these organic compounds have been communicated earlier¹⁻³. The thermal data obtained with the absorbed samples of Ni(II)- and Co(II)-AW500 zeolites have been tabulated (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

Complex formation reactions of pyridine and its derivatives with both cobalt(II) and nickel(II) compounds have been studied by several workers⁴⁻⁷. Cobalt(II) was found to give a chelate with triethanolamine where the ligand was tetradentate giving a trigonal bipyramidal configuration around the metal atom⁸. Nickel(II) on the other hand formed a polycondensed complex with the ligand⁹.

Infrared spectroscopic studies of pyridine adsorption on a series of oxide surfaces, mainly chemically modified SiO_2 , showed that two types of Lewis acid centres were formed differing in the coordination of the exposed central atoms at the surface. Among the bonds formed during adsorption, the coordinate bond of pyridine on electron acceptor centres of surface mixed oxides of SiO_2 was the strongest¹⁰. The same authors¹¹ reported the appearance of a broad, relatively weak band at ~ 2700 cm $^{-1}$ due to pyridine adsorption on various siliceous surfaces. The band was assigned to the $N^+—H$ stretching vibration of pyridinium ions.

In the present study involving pyridine adsorption no clear indication of the nature of interaction is available as neither the temperature of water elimination nor the pattern of thermal decomposition reliably indicates structure or bonding¹². Adsorption of triethanolamine on the zeolites to a considerable extent is however indicated by the presence of an unusually strong exothermic peak in the

TABLE 1—THERMAL DATA OF ZEOLITE SAMPLES

Zeolite	DTA		TGA Weight Loss %
	Endotherm °C	Exotherm °C	
1. Pyridine absorbed-Co(II)-AW500	100, 220, 500 (shallow)	420 (undefined), 540, 780	17 (Two-step)
2. Triethanolamine absorbed Co(II)-AW500	120, 400	300 (shoulder), 360, 460, 760	35 (Three-step)
3. Trichloroethylene absorbed Co(II)-AW500	220, 540 (undefined)	380, 550 (shoulder), 800	16 (Two-step)
4. 1,1,2,2-Tetrachloro-ethane absorbed Co(II)-AW500	100, 220, 500 (shallow)	440 (shoulder), 550, 780	18 (Two-step)
5. Pyridine absorbed- Ni(II)-zeolite	100, 200	400 (shoulder), 480 (hump) 540 (shoulder), 800 (shoulder)	20 (Two-step)
6. Triethanolamine absorbed Ni(II)-AW500	120	360 (shoulder), 440, 800	35 (Three-step)
7. Trichloroethylene absorbed Ni(II)-AW500	100 (undefined), 220	360, 580, (hump), 780 (shoulder)	17 (Two-step)
8. 1,1,2,2-Tetrachloro-ethane absorbed Ni(II)-AW500	100, 220	480, 580, 800 (shoulder)	18 (Two-step)

DTA curve and atleast 3-step weight loss in the TGA curve. But though complex formation is the possible interaction with the zeolites for both pyridine and triethanolamine, the thermal data obtained especially with the former, cannot fully confirm this.

Studies of sigma and pi-bond interactions on the zeolite surface were undertaken with the adsorption of ethane and ethylene on the cation-exchanged forms of zeolite X¹³. Formation of charge transfer complex due to adsorption of tetracyanoethylene onto dehydrated 13X has also been reported¹⁴. Similar reactions are therefore possible involving trichloroethylene and 1, 1, 2, 2-tetrachloroethane on Co(II)-and Ni(II)-exchanged AW500. However, the TGA data of these absorbed samples indicate very low absorption confirming the findings of Lukin *et al.*¹⁵ that zeolites having binders exhibit lower absorption compared to zeolite crystals.

Loss of weight for the zeolite samples is a two-step one except for triethanolamine absorbed samples. For two-step weight loss a faster rate of evolution occurs upto about 200° and a slower rate beyond it. Desorption studies of various substances from zeolites show that dehydration of NaA occurs in two stages, a fast evolution around 100° and a slow evolution at about 300°¹⁶. The triethanolamine absorbed samples of Co(II)-and Ni(II) lose weight in three distinct steps. The rates of loss upto 200° and beyond 300° are slower compared to the rate between 200 and 300° when triethanolamine is desorbed. The other two steps are for dehydration with a maximum rate of loss around 100°. A total weight loss of about 35% is obtained after complete desorption. This figure is much higher than weight losses obtained for other zeolite samples.

The DTA endotherms around 100 and 220° are due to dehydration and beyond 220 occurs desorption of absorbed molecules. These endotherms are mostly shallow and not clearly defined due to very low absorption. Exothermic effects at lower temperatures are for oxidation of the organic molecules while the peaks around 800° indicate thermal

stability of zeolite structures. These exotherms are mostly hump-like peaks with the exception of triethanolamine absorbed zeolites which exhibit very strong oxidation peaks around 450°.

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